

DETERMINATION OF PEROXIDE VALUE OF RANCID FATS. A MODIFIED PROCEDURE

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Peroxide value of the butter-fat has been determined by combining the method of Wheeler and Lea.

Peroxide value is by far the most extensively used index for evaluating rancidity of fats and oils. A number of different iodimetric procedures, viz., those of Lea (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, 108B, 175), Wheeler (*Oil & Soap*, 1932, 9, 89) and Taffel and Revis (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 80, 87T) are available for making such determinations, and although all these methods are presumed to react quantitatively and may do under most conditions, results by the different methods are not always reliable. The experience of the present investigator with peroxide determination using the three methods is that Lea's method gives lower values than Wheeler's and still lower values are obtained with the Taffel-Revis's method. The results were found to differ depending on the following factors: (i) the atmosphere in which the estimation is carried out, (ii) the temperature, (iii) the time of reaction and (iv) weight of fat used in the estimation.

For this reason all the methods were subjected to re-examination using different weights of fat, different reaction period and using different temperatures, as also determinations were made both in presence of oxygen and in inert atmospheres. The experimental results with a sample of rancid butter-fat are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Determination of peroxide value by different methods.

Wt. of fat.	Time of reaction.	Temp.	Atmosphere.	Peroxide value.
1. Lea's method.				
1.008 g.	3 minutes	98.8°	Nitrogen	95.80
2.100	"	"	"	95.10
0.5020	"	"	"	95.88
0.2510	"	"	"	95.93
10.1000	"	"	"	93.05
2. Wheeler's method.				
5.5625 g.	1 minute	36-37°	Air	103.6
3.5163	"	"	"	104.7
7.8203	"	"	"	101.9
1.0035	"	"	"	104.5
10.0	"	"	"	98.0
3. Taffel-Revis method.				
1.0 g.	2-3 minutes	98.8°	CO ₂	91.81
2.0	"	"	"	89.62
5.0	"	"	"	88.07
10.0	"	"	"	86.82

From the results in Table I it is evident that the Wheeler method always gives higher values than the Lea or Taffel-Revis method. This can be explained firstly as due to the inert atmospheres maintained in the other two methods, whereas in the Wheeler method the atmospheric oxygen liberates a certain amount of iodine from the KI solution. The lower values in Lea's method may, however, be due to the fact that there is a possible chance of partial decomposition of the peroxides at the high temperature employed. The still lower values obtained with the Taffel-Revis method are probably due to the incomplete extraction of the peroxides with the acetic acid alone. The use of chloroform is a probable advantage with the Lea or Wheeler method. Thus a point of considerable importance in the peroxide determination is the *atmosphere* in which the reaction is conducted, as also the *temperature* of the reaction.

The Effect of Weight of Fat.—The next variable studied was the weight of fat used in the experiment, using a temperature of 36°-37° (Wheeler), an atmosphere of CO₂ (Taffel-Revis) and a reaction period of 2-3 minutes (Lea) and Table II shows the effect of sample size on the peroxide value.

TABLE II

Peroxide value and sample size.

Wt. of fat. (butter-fat).	Peroxide value.	Wt. of fat. (butter-fat).	Peroxide value.
0.1025	97.22	1.5129	96.83
0.2050	97.22	2.0100	96.02
0.4110	97.03	5.1035	93.0
1.0030	96.84	9.9877	92.85

TABLE III

Effect of sample size on peroxide value.

Coconut oil		Groundnut oil		Linseed oil	
Wt. of fat.	Peroxide value.	Wt. of fat.	Peroxide value.	Wt. of fat.	Peroxide value.
0.1230 g.	9.2	0.1532 g.	26.0	0.1028 g.	27.4
0.2526	9.2	0.3185	25.3	0.2550	25.9
1.0257	8.9	0.8241	23.5	0.7574	23.4
2.0512	8.8	1.5656	22.2	1.2022	20.2
5.0	8.1	2.9400	20.4	2.5110	18.2
		5.0	17.8	5.0	15.0

Comparison of the results obtained by Lea's method in Table I with those obtained in Table II clearly shows that in the original method of Lea there is a slight decomposition of the peroxide at the high temperature (about 1-2%). The peroxide value of a particular sample of oxidised fat is moreover found to vary considerably with the weight of the fat. This is probably due to the re-absorption of the liberated iodine at the unsaturated centres of the fat. This is more fully illustrated by the results in Table III where

similar experiments have been conducted with rancid coconut, groundnut, and linseed oils, the re-absorption of iodine by the oils being least with coconut and maximum with the linseed oil as the sample size is varied from 0.1 to 5.0 g. The error due to this source may be reduced by restricting the weight of the fat to the lower value employed in the *Les's* method, viz. 1 g.

Effect of Reaction Time.—The next object was to study the effect of time factor on the peroxide value determinations. The following table (Table IV) records the results of such investigations using different reaction periods in the dark including those used by previous workers. In order to keep the weight of the fat constant and thus to minimise the effect due to this factor, nearly 1.0 g. of fat was used in these experiments, by taking the same measured volume of a chloroform solution containing a definite weight of the oxidised butter-fat.

TABLE IV
Peroxide values vs time.
In CO₂ atmosphere at 37°.

Wt. of fat.	Time.	Peroxide value.	Wt. of fat.	Time.	Peroxide value.
1.0244	3.5 mins.	95.0	1.0460	2 hours	97.5
1.0460	10	95.5	"	4	97.5
"	15	96.2	"	6	97.5
"	30	97.3	"	12	97.7
"	45	97.5	"	24	98.2
"	60	97.5	"	48	98.93

Fig. 1

From the results in the above table it appears that almost 98% of the peroxide react within 3 to 5 minutes. For complete reaction of the peroxides with KI, it is better to allow one hour reaction time in the dark, as a safe measure. This is quite evident from the flat portion of the curve in Fig. 1 relating peroxide value and time factor.

Recommended Procedure.—For accurate determination of the peroxide the following procedure may therefore be used with advantage. About 1 g. of the oil or fat is weighed into a 750 c.c. glass-stoppered iodine bottle from which air has previously been excluded by flushing with carbon dioxide for 3 to 5 minutes, and 10 c.c. of a solvent comprising 40 parts of CHCl_3 and 60 parts of acetic acid (glacial, A.R.) are added to dissolve the fat. The solvent mixture must previously be flushed with CO_2 for 5 to 10 minutes before use to exclude any dissolved air; 2 c.c. of a saturated solution of KI is next added and the stopper, moistened with KI solution, is carefully put in place and the whole kept in the dark for one hour (at 36° - 37°) after which the liberated iodine is titrated with $N/200$ -thiosulphate solution after diluting the reaction mixture with oxygen-free distilled water. Lea's procedure for carrying out the titration in a dark room illuminated by a tungsten lamp is definitely an advantage in determining the end-point with the starch indicator. The result is expressed as ml. 0.002*N*-thiosulphate per g. of fat.

The method combines the essential features of the Wheeler's and Lea's method in that an inert atmosphere as used by Lea has been employed, the temperature used being that of Wheeler's, viz. 36° - 37° , at which the chance of decomposition of peroxide is nil and the weight of the fat has been confined to that used by Lea, viz. 1 g. to minimise the effect of re-absorption of iodine which will necessarily entail greater error when larger amount of fat is used, as in the original Wheeler's process. The results obtained by the modified method approach most closely to those obtained by Lea's method.

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